

STRENGTH AND RELIABILITY OF SILICON CARBIDE WHISKER REINFORCED
ALUMINUM COMPOSITES BY SQUEEZE CASTING INCLUDING A VACUUM SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites were prepared by the squeeze casting method, to evaluate the reliability of the strength, and the size effect based on Weibull's distribution function. All the specimens tested at room and evaluated temperature were checked the bending strength and fracture origin by SEM. The composites were observed to have three kinds of brittle fracture modes which were distinguished from the fracture origin, of the inside, of the surface and of the corner of the specimen. A bi-modal Weibull distribution based on the effective volume and surface area was applied to the strength distribution of the composites. In the model, the fracture of the composites was determined by a competing-risk model among the defect of several kinds of the sub-populations. The analytical results by the bi-modal Weibull distribution was in a better agreement with the experimental data than those by the single Weibull distributions. Additionally, the vacuum squeeze casting, by which the air in the whisker-preform was exhausted, revealed to increase in the bending strength about 6% and to improve the reliability. Air exhausting affected on the size of the defect in the composites, resulting to change the fracture sites from the surface to the inner.

INTRODUCTION

The silicon-carbide whisker reinforced aluminum alloy has demonstrated to have excellent mechanical, physical properties and productivity, and it can be shaped, machined, drilled, ground, etc. using conventional

manufacturing facilities. Increasing number of papers on the composites is now leading it to practical uses. For the latest two-year, there can be encountered vigorous reports on the bending strength [1,7], tensile strength [1, 2,5,6,8-11,14-16], fracture toughness [2,4,14,27], fatigue [2,5,15,26], creep [12,13], wear [11,16], microstructure [3], heat treatment [2,4,6,9,14], modulus [1,9-11,14,17,21,27], matrix alloy [2,6,7,9,10], super plasticity [19, 20], interfacial strength [18] and fabrication method [10,11,15-17]. However, the statistical treatment of the composites caused by the scatter of the strength are not still established. The study into reliability becomes of important for the application to structural components, machine parts and so on. We previously reported [1] on the mechanical properties of three kinds of ceramic whisker reinforced aluminum composites, i.e. by silicon nitride, silicon carbide and potassium titanate whiskers, prepared by squeeze casting method. Then, silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites exhibited the highest strength and elasticity in the range of 30% to 40% volume fraction of whisker, but the scatter of the strength was also larger than others. Mcdaniels [9] pointed out that the silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites were failed in a brittle manner at 30% to 40% volume fraction of whisker with a low failure strain, but the ultimate strength was gradually increased with an increase of the volume fraction. To give the best use of such a high strength composites, it is necessary to evaluate it from the statistical point of view.

The present paper deals with the strength of silicon-carbide reinforced aluminum composites and determine the strength distribution as the random variable. It was observed that the composites were fractured from the defect existing in the inside, the surface and the corner of the specimen. Then, multi-modal Weibull distribution [22,23] was applied by the concept that the fracture of the composites were determined by the competition of the strength distributions of several defect's sub-populations in a specimen. Additionally, the effect of vacuum squeeze casting on the strength of the composites was investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The silicon carbide whisker produced by Tokai Carbon Co., Ltd. (hereinafter, referred to as "SiC whisker") was used as reinforcement materials. The whiskers are β -SiC with diameters ranging about 0.05 μm to 0.2 μm , and the original length is from 10 μm to 40 μm . And the density of the whisker is 3.17Mg/m³. As metal matrix, pure aluminum (99.9%Al, 0.06%Fe, 0.04%Si) which is widely employed in a light metal material was used.

Squeeze casting method was applied to the preparation of the SiC whisker reinforced aluminum composites (hereinafter, referred to as "SiCw/Al composites"). The outline of the apparatus is shown in Fig.1. SiCw/Al composites are prepared as follows. Firstly, the whiskers are filled into the flame ②, which is attached to an electrical furnace. Then, the volume fraction of whisker (hereinafter, referred to as "V_w") was given by controlling a total weight of whisker and the displacement of the rod ①. In the present work, 30%V_w was employed with the aim of preparing the high strength and high modulus composites. The whisker ③ was pre-heated for 10min at 600°C. After that, molten aluminum at a temperature of 700°C is poured into the flame ②, and forcibly infiltrated into the whisker preform by the rod ① to solidify with a pressure of 49MPa for 1min using a program-controlled universal tester (Shimazu Servo-Pulser, EHF-10). In the case of vacuum squeeze casting, immediately after pouring, the burst

Figure 1. Outline of the apparatus preparing the composites.

Figure 2. Specimen subjected to 4-point bending load.

exhausting system operates to evacuate the cavity of the preform from the bottom of it as shown in Fig.1.

The strength of SiCw/Al composites was evaluated by 3-point and 4-point bending tests. The specimens were machined in the size of 4mm width, 2mm, 4mm and 6mm thicknesses and 36mm length. Each specimen was finished with the accuracy of $\pm 0.1\text{mm}$ by abrasive papers. The 3-point and 4-point bending tests were carried out with 30mm span and with 10mm inner span and 30mm outer span, respectively, at testing speed of 0.5mm/min. Then, the bending strength σ is generally given by the following equation replacing the size shown in Fig.2;

$$\sigma = \frac{3WL_1}{4bh^2} \quad (1)$$

Where, W is a fracture load. The number of the specimen was about 10 for each size and each test. After the test, the fracture surface of each specimen was observed by SEM (Scanning electron microscope) in order to identify the defect causing the fracture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bending Strength and Fracture Mode

The results of the bending test of SiCw/Al composites are shown in Table 1. It is seen from the table that the average bending strength of the composites are nearly 700MPa at the 3-point bending test and about 620MPa to

TABLE 1. Results of 3-point and 4-point bending tests.

Test	$b \times 2h$ (mm^2)	N	Ave. (MPa)	C.V. (%)
3-point	4×2	10	697	9.15
	4×4	10	695	10.42
	4×6	9	685	9.73
4-point	4×2	8	621	10.74
	4×4	11	629	6.38
	4×6	8	619	7.37

N: Number of specimen.

Ave.: Average bending strength.

C.V.: Coefficient of variation.

630MPa at the 4-point bending test. And the coefficients of variations, which are in the range of about 6% to 11% depending on the test condition, are very large as compared with wrought metal materials. It is noted that the average bending strength is slightly decreased as the thickness of the specimen becomes large.

Figures 3(a), (b) and (c) show the fractographs of the SiCw/Al composites by SEM. The photos demonstrate that the composites have three kinds of fracture modes. Each fracture mode caused by the defect existing in the inside, the surface or the corner of the specimen as indicated by arrows, respectively. And the composites are characterized by being failed

Figure 3. Fractographs of SiCw/Al composites.

- (a) Fracture caused by the inner defect.
- (b) Fracture caused by the surface defect.
- (c) Fracture caused by the corner defect.

Figure 4. Comparison of strength distribution of 4mm thickness composites between conventional and vacuum squeeze casting, showing defect type, Weibull parameters and normal distribution parameters.

in the brittle manner, as reported by McDaniels [9]. Here, the surface results in a flat-like plane perpendicular to the maximum tensile stress on the specimen. The defect in the inside is observed to be a "void" type. Such a defect is referred to the reference [14] as the so-called "fish-eye". The defects in the surface and the corner are probably a "flaw" type which may be extrinsically occurred during machining or handling of the specimen. The incidence of the corner fracture is little, and that of the surface fracture is more often than of the inner fracture.

Effect of Vacuum Squeeze Casting

Figure 4 shows weibull plots of the 3-point bending strength of the 4mm thickness composites fabricated by conventional and vacuum squeeze casting. In the figure, Weibull parameters deduced by the following paragraph, are attached. From the experimental data, the vacuum processing improves the mean strength, and also reduces the scatter. The possible reason is, that the inherited cavity formed in casting decreases in the size and the number by the vacuum casting. It is supported by the SEM observation, consequently, the incidence of the inner fracture increases on the vacuum squeeze casting.

Distribution of Bending Strength

Statistical procedure There are three kinds of the brittle fracture modes in SiCw/Al composites, as mentioned above, depending on the defect inheriting in the inside, the surface and the corner of the specimen. Such a characteristics has been similarly observed in the failure of high strength structural ceramics [25,26]. Here, it may be introduced, the Weibull's distribution function based on the weakest link model to the strength distribution of the composites. In the present analysis, it is carried out on the assumption that a fracture occurs only at the tensile stress field on the specimen, while the fracture occurred from the side surface is negligible. The distribution functions $F(\sigma)$ of the strength σ are given by the

following three equations depending on the kind of the fracture mode[22];

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp(-B_1), \quad B_1 = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{01}}\right)^{m_1} V_e, \quad V_e = \frac{bh}{m_1+1} \left(\frac{2L_1}{m_1+1} + L_2\right) \quad (2)$$

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp(-B_2), \quad B_2 = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{02}}\right)^{m_2} A_e, \quad A_e = b \left(\frac{2L_1}{m_2+1} + L_2\right) \quad (3)$$

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp(-B_3), \quad B_3 = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{03}}\right)^{m_3} L_e, \quad L_e = \frac{4L_1}{m_3+1} + 2L_2 \quad (4)$$

Where, m_i ($i=1-3$) is a shape parameter, σ_{0i} ($i=1-3$) is a scale parameter, V_e , A_e , L_e : the effective volume, the effective surface area and the effective length, respectively. In case of 3-point bending test, L_2 is equivalent to 0. We consider, eqs.(2)-(4) are realizable if the fracture mode is governed by one kind of defect's sub-population. In case that the strength distribution is determined by the competition among the defect's several kinds of sub-populations, $F(\sigma)$ is given as follows[22,23];

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp\left(-\sum_{i=1}^k B_i\right) \quad (5)$$

where, k : a positive integer. The Weibull parameters are found by the maximum likelihood estimation method. Especially, the multi-step maximum likelihood estimation method is employed to the multi-modal Weibull distribution, by which the Weibull parameters can be found for each fracture mode. Then, the likelihood equations are as follows[22,23], e.g. in case of $i=1$ in eq.(5);

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{1}{m_1} + \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \ln \sigma_j - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_j^{m_1} \cdot \ln \sigma_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \sigma_j^{m_1}} &= 0 \\ \sigma_{01} &= \left(\frac{V_e}{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \sigma_j^{m_1}\right)^{1/m_1} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Where, n is a total number of samples, and n_1 is a number of samples broken by the cause of the inner defect at stress $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_{n_1}$. The average strengths $\bar{\sigma}$ of eqs.(2),(3) and (4) are generally given as follows;

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_{01} V_e^{-1/m_1} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m_1}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_{02} A_e^{-1/m_2} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m_2}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_{03} L_e^{-1/m_3} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m_3}\right) \quad (9)$$

Where, Γ means a gamma function. The average strength of eq.(5) is not obtained as an analytical value, so it can be found by integrating numerically as follows;

$$\bar{\sigma} = \int_0^{\infty} \{1 - F(\sigma)\} d\sigma \quad (10)$$

TABLE 2. Weibull parameters of 2mm thickness composites given by the maximum likelihood estimation method.

Test	eq.	m_1	m_2	σ_{01}	σ_{02}
3-point	(2)	15.2	-	686	-
	(3)	-	15.2	-	824
	(5)	19.7	14.0	767	849
4-point	(2)	10.3	-	746	-
	(3)	-	10.3	-	943
	(5)	17.2	7.61	762	1139

Figure 5. Weibull plots of SiCw/Al composites at the size of 2mm thickness.

Figure 6. Average bending strength of SiCw/Al composites.

Analytical results

Table 2 shows the Weibull parameters estimated at 2mm thickness specimens. Here, the fracture mode was regarded as two cases, that is the inside fracture ($i=1$) and the surface fracture ($i=2$) because the incidence of the corner fracture was very little, however, in case of eq.(5), it is taken as the censored data into consideration. For the calculated Weibull parameters based on eqs.(2) and (3), the shape parameters have quite the same value, and the scale parameters are somewhat different. On the contrary, in case of the bi-modal Weibull distribution given by eq.(5), each Weibull parameter appears clearly to differ. That is to say, shape parameters m_1 due to the inner defect tend to be larger than the parameters m_2 due to the surface defect for both tests. The Weibull plots of the bending strength of 2mm thickness composites are shown in Fig.5. The solid lines in the figure mean the distribution curves of eq.(5), and the dotted lines show the distribution lines of eqs.(2) and (3), which are based on the Weibull parameters estimated at 4-point bending test on the Table 2. Both analytical curves are in a good agreement with the experimental plots. In particular, the curves obtained from eq.(5) reproduce well the experimental plots of the low strength region, because each Weibull parameter is estimated depending on the fracture mode of the individual data and in the region the fracture mode caused by the surface defect gives a more failure probability.

The average strength of the different thickness specimen are predicted as shown in Fig.6. The values are calculated on the basis of the Weibull

parameters estimated at 2mm thickness specimen. Then, eq.(10) is given by the bi-modal Weibull distribution based on the effective volume and surface area. The analytical curves of eqs.(8) and (10) are in a good agreement with the experimental data. On the other hand, the curves of eq.(7) underestimates the strength with an increase in the thickness, because it misunderstands many of the data failed due to the surface defect, so that the influence of the effective volume is little. Nevertheless, the size effect given by only the thickness is taken in eq.(7) into consideration. The analytical values by eq.(8) is horizontal, but the values of eq.(10) is slightly decreased as the thickness increases. The reason is that the Weibull parameters estimated from a few data caused by the inner defect are also included in eq.(10). As the strength level can not be kept constant with increase in the thickness, the prediction by eq.(10) is reasonable. Therefore, the bi-modal Weibull distribution is the most suitable distribution for the strength distribution of the composites.

CONCLUSION

For the purpose of evaluating reliability, the silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites were prepared by the conventional and vacuum squeeze casting. The 3-point and 4-point bending tests were carried out, and all the fracture surfaces were observed by SEM to check the site of the fracture. The results are summarized as follows,

- 1) The average bending strengths of the 30%Vw composites were nearly 700MPa at the 3-point bending test and about 620MPa to 630MPa at the 4-point bending test, and the coefficient of variations were in the range of about 6% to 11% for each test condition.
- 2) The vacuum squeeze casting improved the strength of the composites about 6%, and increased the incidence of the inner fracture.
- 3) The composites were observed to have three kinds of brittle fracture modes which were occurred from a defect existing in the inside, the surface or the corner of the specimen. The strength distribution of the composites was evaluated by a bi-modal Weibull distribution function based on the effective volume and surface area.
- 4) The analytical values gave a better agreement with the experimental data than those derived from single Weibull distributions based on the effective volume and the effective surface area.

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